

PERSPECTIVES OF USING DECENTRALIZED FINANCES IN MODERN ECONOMY

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***Abstract.** The development of blockchain technology has given rise to decentralized finance (DeFi), a transformative approach to banking, investing, and overall financial management, fundamentally reshaping the modern economy. DeFi represents a paradigm shift from traditional financial systems by leveraging blockchain's inherent properties – decentralization, transparency, security, and inclusivity. These factors are driving interest and investment in DeFi, leading to its increased adoption in the broader economy. Based on the data and analysis - the global DeFi market is expected to expand significantly, with projections reaching USD 231.19 billion by 2030, marking a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 46.0% from 2023 to 2030.*

In addition to market capitalization, there are also multiple examples of innovations, which are driven by decentralized finance – such as non-fungible tokens, yield farming, decentralized identity and credit scoring. The world of decentralized finance (DeFi) holds immense potential, much of which remains largely unexplored. While the initial waves of DeFi innovation have introduced groundbreaking concepts such as decentralized exchanges (DEXs), lending platforms, and yield farming, this is merely the tip of the iceberg.

However, while the adoption of Decentralized Finance (DeFi) brings various benefits, it also requires significant caution due to inherent risks – such as smart contract vulnerabilities, regulatory uncertainty, market liquidity risks, lack of consumer protection, scalability and performance issue, and high risk of fraud. There are multiple causes of risks in decentralized environment – but the main problems associated with it are technical complexity, regulatory gaps and market volatility and liquidity.

This paper aims to define perspectives of DeFi usage by exploring the potential of DeFi and blockchain technology in the context of modern economy. Also, this paper focuses on the risk management concept – explaining the main problems which can be faced while using the decentralized approach to finances and suggesting the way to minimize these risks.

Keywords: *Decentralized Finances, Smart Contract, Blockchain, Ethereum, Cryptocurrency, Software, Economy, Regulations.*

Introduction. Recently, the popularity of using decentralized approach to finances has been growing rapidly. This surge in decentralized finances (or DeFi) has been sparked by revolutionary transformations in the digital finance sector. Digital finances represent a segment of the financial market, which provides services via the Internet, being accessible by any modern device (e.g personal computer, smartphone, or laptop). DeFi provides the same services but offering multiple benefits for the end users – such as eliminating intermediary delays and failures, reducing transaction costs, and minimizing credit risk in lending. Examples of products in DeFi ecosystem include Bitcoin, Ethereum, stablecoins (USDT, USDC, etc.) and non-fungible tokens (NFTs).

Analysis of recent research and publication. As already mentioned, the usage of decentralized approach in finances is growing rapidly. The current state of decentralized finances market is well presented in recent research – the market has grown exponentially in recent years. It is expected to grow from \$21.21 billion in

2023 to \$30.17 billion in 2024 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 42.2% [1]. Overall the global DeFi market is expected to expand significantly, with projections reaching USD 231.19 billion by 2030, marking a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 46.0% from 2023 to 2030 [2].

Innovations within the DeFi sector are driving growth, with blockchain technology playing a pivotal role. This includes the integration of smart contracts and decentralized applications (dApps) that enhance transaction efficiency and security.

DeFi is also being actively researched from the technical point of view. There are multiple focuses – such as comparing CeFi and DeFi [3], investigating the smart contracts [4] and other concepts, which are mentioned further in the article.

Purpose and objectives of the article. The aim of this work is to review existing research and developments in the realm of decentralized finance (DeFi) and synthesize existing studies and developments in DeFi to assist in evaluating the relevance, advantages, weaknesses, and challenges of decentralized financial systems. The purpose of this review is to define whether DeFi is a worthy innovation to support in the modern economy.

Additionally, this review aims to define the perspective usages based on the DeFi key qualities, and not only capture the current state of DeFi, but to also shed light on important areas for future academic exploration within this financial innovation.

Basic concepts. To analyze the perspective of using decentralized finances in the modern economy, several basic concepts need to be outlined. Also, there is a need to establish the conceptual framework to define technical aspects of DeFi – which can help us to identify the advantages and drawbacks of using it.

Decentralized finance is a wide term for all financial products and services that are built on public, open source blockchains. There are several definitions of decentralized finance, or DeFi, in the literature – varying by the level of technical depth and abstraction.

The most simple and abstract definition is the following - decentralized financial system is a system, which offers financial instruments without relying on intermediaries (such as banks or brokers). Some papers [5] define decentralized finance as the transformation of traditional financial products into products that work without an intermediary using smart contracts on the blockchain. Also, decentralized finances can be defined as an ecosystem of financial applications that are developed and implemented using blockchain technology and a distributed ledger.

Some authors define decentralized finance as an ecosystem of decentralized applications that provide financial services built using peer-to-peer and trustless networks [6].

As we can see, the main thing that connects these definitions is a blockchain – the most important technology in the decentralization paradigm, which makes it possible. Also, the "peer-to-peer and trustless networks" are emphasized – which describes the fundamental concept of networks used in DeFi. The research [7] points out that decentralized finance uses smart contracts to create protocols that replicate existing financial services in a more open, interoperable, and transparent way.

Based on these definitions, we can describe the decentralized finance as a peer-to-peer financial system that uses smart contracts based on a distributed ledger to ensure its integrity and security. The main purpose of this system is to provide an alternative to the traditional (centralized) financial system, introducing multiple benefits to the end users.

Technical Implementation. From the technical perspective, there are several technologies and concepts which make DeFi possible: blockchain, distributed ledger technology (DLT) and smart contracts.

A blockchain is a decentralized system that records transactions across multiple computers in a way that ensures data integrity, security, and transparency. The main characteristics of the blockchain are the following:

1. Structure: Blockchain consists of a chain of blocks, where each block contains a list of transactions. Once a block is added to the chain, the information it contains cannot be altered.

2. Cryptographic Hash: Each block is linked to the previous block using a cryptographic hash, creating a chain that makes it very difficult to alter information retroactively.

3. Consensus Mechanism: Blockchain networks typically have consensus mechanisms like Proof of Work (PoW) or Proof of Stake (PoS). These mechanisms ensure that all participants agree on the state of the ledger and prevent malicious activities.

4. Decentralization: Unlike traditional databases, blockchain data is not stored in a central location. Instead, it is distributed across a network of computers (nodes), making it more resistant to tampering or failure.

5. Multiple Applications: While blockchain is widely known for powering cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and Ethereum, it has a range of applications beyond digital currencies, such as supply chain management, digital identity verification, and smart contracts.

A distributed ledger is a digital system for recording transactions and data across multiple locations simultaneously, ensuring that the information is securely stored and verified by a decentralized network of computers, making it resistant to tampering and providing transparency and security without a central authority. From the technical perspective, distributed ledger is "a database that is shared and synchronized across networks distributed across multiple sites, institutions, or geographic regions, allowing a transaction to have multiple private or public 'witnesses'" [8]. This definition implies that there is a network of servers with a distributed database, and all servers share the same data – functioning as a ledger.

The most important aspects of distributed ledgers are having no central administration and no centralized data storage, which makes it “distributed”. The

main advantage of using the distributed ledger lies in significantly reducing the risk of data manipulation, which is very important in context of financial services.

The easiest way to understand the principle behind the distributed ledgers is to compare them to more traditional analogue – the centralized ledger. Let's consider an example of storing an information in a centralized registry. Typically, this registry is managed by a single individual (or team). In this scenario we have multiple risks, which can occur:

1. Data manipulation risk. If the person (or team) responsible for managing the centralized registry is untrustworthy – it can result in data manipulation, which is nearly impossible to detect.

2. Cyberattack risk. Any computer system is vulnerable to hacking (to a certain extent).

3. Hardware risk. If the hardware hosting the registry is damaged – we can lose an access to the data.

However, in a distributed system all these risks are eliminated. The data can't be neither corrupted nor manipulated due to the absence of a single storage or a single party managing the data. The cyberattack risk is not completely eliminated, but the difficulty of such attack increases exponentially due to the distributed nature of the system and large number of servers.

Another important innovation in the context of decentralization are smart contracts. Smart contracts are self-executing and self-verifying computers programs, encoding the agreement between several parties. The main purpose of a smart contract is to automate the interaction between users, ensuring that transactions are traceable and irreversible.

Smart contract driven processes can occur through and be recorded in distributed ledgers secured by blockchain. This combination forms the fundamentals of decentralized finances.

The concept of cloud computing is also worth mentioning. While it's not mandatory for the DeFi implementation, many decentralized platforms use it. Cloud

computing refers to the delivery of various services over the internet, including storage, processing power, databases, networking, software, and analytics. It allows users to access and store data and applications on remote servers rather than on local devices, providing flexibility, scalability, and cost-efficiency. The whole concept of cloud computing is similar to the concept of decentralization. That's why almost everything in the sphere of DeFi benefits from cloud computing – e.g. decentralized exchanges (DEXs), lending platforms, yield farming and staking of cryptocurrencies.

Usage Perspectives. By utilizing technologies, which are fundamental to the concept of decentralization, decentralized finances provide multiple opportunities and improvements to traditional financial models. Such improvements include (but not limited to):

Accessibility and inclusivity: DeFi platforms operate on open blockchain networks, making them accessible to anyone with an internet connection, regardless of their geographical location or financial status. This accessibility helps to democratize financial services, enabling people who are unbanked or underbanked to participate in the global economy.

Transparency: Blockchain technology ensures that all transactions on DeFi platforms are transparent and can be audited by anyone. This level of transparency helps to build trust among users and can reduce the risk of fraud and corruption.

Interoperability: Many DeFi applications are built on compatible blockchain networks like Ethereum, allowing them to interact seamlessly with each other. This interoperability enables the creation of complex financial services and allows users to move assets across different DeFi platforms without intermediaries.

Censorship Resistance: DeFi operates on decentralized networks that are not controlled by any single entity, making it difficult for any party to freeze accounts or block transactions. This is particularly beneficial for users in politically unstable or oppressive countries.

Programmability: Smart contracts automate transactions and enforce agreements without the need for intermediaries. This programmability enables the

creation of complex financial instruments, such as synthetic assets, derivatives, and automated lending and borrowing systems.

Lowering the Costs: By eliminating middlemen and reducing the need for manual handling, DeFi can significantly lower transaction fees and administrative costs associated with financial services.

Innovation: The open-source nature of DeFi platforms encourages continuous development and innovation, allowing developers to build upon existing protocols and create new financial products and services.

Considering the described advantages of decentralized finances, we can now identify promising perspectives and use cases of using DeFi across various sectors and functionalities:

1. **Banking the Unbanked:** One of the most impactful perspectives of DeFi is providing financial services to the unbanked or underbanked populations. By offering easy access to banking services, savings accounts, and low-cost money transfers through mobile devices, DeFi has the potential to revolutionize financial inclusion worldwide.

2. **Cross-Border Payments and Remittances:** DeFi can streamline and reduce the cost of remittances and other cross-border payments. Traditional remittance services often come with high fees and slow processing times, but DeFi solutions can offer faster, cheaper alternatives without the need for currency conversion or third-party intermediaries.

3. **Wealth Management and Investment:** DeFi platforms can democratize access to investment opportunities, from simple interest-earning accounts to more complex financial instruments like derivatives and synthetic assets. This could enable a broader range of investors to access wealth-building tools previously reserved for high-net-worth individuals or institutional investors.

4. **Decentralized Exchanges (DEXs):** DEXs allow users to trade assets directly with one another without the need for a centralized authority. This not only increases

security by reducing the risk of exchange hacks but also enhances privacy and reduces trading fees.

5. Insurance: DeFi can offer innovative insurance products with automated claims processing and without traditional insurance brokers. Smart contracts can automatically execute claims based on predefined criteria, reducing the possibility of disputes and fraud.

6. Credit and Lending: Through DeFi, individuals and businesses can obtain loans without going through traditional credit checks, relying instead on digital collateral. This system can potentially offer more competitive rates and open up new avenues for lending and borrowing.

7. Enterprise Use Cases: Enterprises could leverage DeFi for various purposes, including automated payroll systems, real-time financial audits, and supply chain financing. This could improve efficiency and transparency in corporate financial management.

Another thing worth mentioning – is that the concept of decentralized finances is not necessarily used as a substitute for traditional finances (TradFi). As DeFi matures, we might see more hybrid models where DeFi interfaces seamlessly with traditional financial institutions, offering customers the best of both worlds. This could include DeFi platforms underpinned by traditional financial principles but enhanced with the efficiency and innovation of blockchain technology. We can already see such examples using blockchain bridges and wrapped tokens.

Risk management. While there are multiple opportunities of using DeFi in the modern economy – it is still heavily regulated, and its degree of adoption heavily varies in each country. The main reason behind it are the risks caused by the DeFi implementation.

Such risks include smart contract vulnerabilities, market volatility, and regulatory uncertainty. Smart contract bugs or exploits can lead to significant financial losses, as these contracts are often immutable once deployed. Market volatility can result in rapid and substantial changes in asset values, potentially

leading to liquidation events and loss of collateral. Regulatory uncertainty poses the risk of legal repercussions and changes in the operational landscape for DeFi projects.

To mitigate these risks, it is crucial to conduct thorough smart contract audits and use well-established protocols. Diversifying investments and employing risk management strategies can help manage market volatility. Staying informed about regulatory developments and ensuring compliance with local laws can reduce the risk of legal issues. Additionally, using decentralized insurance protocols can offer a safety net against potential losses.

Also, another approach for managing the DeFi risks is using a hybrid system – combining the decentralized system with the traditional financial system. This approach allows a certain degree of manual regulation – which goes against a full decentralization principle, but is definitely helpful in context of legal compliance and investors safety.

Conclusions and prospects for further development. In conclusion, Decentralized Finance (DeFi) stands as a highly relevant and progressively influential sector within the broader financial landscape. Rooted in blockchain technology, DeFi offers numerous advantages over traditional financial systems, including enhanced accessibility, improved transparency, greater interoperability, robust security features, and the elimination of intermediaries, which collectively lead to reduced costs and improved efficiency.

However, engaging with DeFi involves certain risks. There are several issues to be addressed – such as smart contract vulnerabilities, the volatility of crypto assets, regulatory uncertainty, and the lack of recourse in dispute resolutions. These risks are the reason why decentralized finances currently is heavily regulated and requires careful assessment and a deep understanding of the underlying technologies and market dynamics.

The potential use cases of DeFi extend far beyond its current applications, promising transformative impacts across various domains. These range from providing essential financial services to the unbanked populations of the world,

facilitating more efficient and less expensive cross-border transactions, to innovating in areas such as insurance, lending, and personal wealth management. Moreover, the evolving convergence of DeFi with traditional finance suggests a future where both systems coexist and complement each other, leading to a more inclusive and flexible financial ecosystem. These opportunities create a significant space for the further research – not only from the technical perspective, but especially in the context of risk management, which is one of the hardest challenges DeFi faces right now.

As DeFi continues to evolve and mature, its integration with established financial norms and regulatory frameworks will be crucial. The successful fusion of these two worlds not only paves the way for groundbreaking financial products and services but also ensures that the benefits of DeFi can be used on a global scale, making it an indispensable part of the financial sector's future. This will create a balanced approach that embraces the innovative potential of DeFi while adequately addressing its inherent risks.

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